

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART XIII*. SYNTHESIS
OF 4:5- AND 4:8-DIMETHYLEUDALENES.

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To serve as reference compounds, 4:5- and 4:8-dimethyleudalenes have been synthesised and suitably characterised. Incidentally, a simpler preparation of 4-methyleudalene has been achieved.

In the study of sesquiterpenoids alkylcadalenes (Campbell and Soffer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 417; Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1948, **25**, 69, 315; Gupta and Muthana, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1953, **35**, 131, 259, 310) and alkyleudalenes (Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, **16**, 268; Bradfield *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 667, 673, 1137, 1141; 1937, 760, 763; Gupta and Muthana, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1953, **35**, 263, 307) serve as useful reference compounds. This communication describes the syntheses of 4:8- and 4:5-dimethyleudalenes.

4:8-Dimethyleudalene (VI)

This hydrocarbon has been synthesised by an extension of the succinic anhydride synthesis (Berliner, "Organic Reactions", Vol. 5, 1949, p. 229; Sukh Dev and Guha, this *Journal*, 1948, **25**, 13). The Friedel-Crafts condensation of isopropylsuccinic anhydride with *p*-xylene in nitrobenzene solution afforded α -isopropyl- β -(2:5-dimethylbenzoyl)-propionic acid (I). In analogy with the reaction of methylsuccinic anhydride with aromatic hydrocarbons (vide Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*) and in accordance with the theoretical principles (Desai and Wali, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **6A**, 135; Wali *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1941, **14A**, 139; Rothstein and Saboor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 425) governing these condensations, the product was expected to have the desired structure. However, further evidence in favour of this structure was obtained by its conversion into the diketocarboxylic acid (II) via its isonitroso derivative; oxidative cleavage of (II) with alkaline hydrogen peroxide furnished 2:5-dimethylbenzoic acid and isopropylmalonic acid.

The Clemmensen reduction of the keto-acid (I) proceeded smoothly to yield α -isopropyl- γ -(2:5-dimethylphenyl)-butyric acid (III). The latter on intramolecular acylation with polyphosphoric acid (PPA) afforded the tetralone (IV) in good yield. The ketone was inert to the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine even under forcing conditions (Josten, *Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 2230; Szmant and McGinnis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2890; Sonntag *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 2283).

* Part XII. This *Journal*, 1952, **29**, 721.

The above ketone on the Clemmensen reduction, followed by sulphur-dehydrogenation, afforded the known 4-methyleudalene (V) (Ruzicka *et al.*, *loc. cit.*); this constituted a far superior synthesis of 4-methyleudalene.

The tetralone (IV) was treated with methyl lithium and the crude tertiary alcohol, thus obtained, was dehydrated with formic acid to yield the 5:6-dihydro derivative of (VI). The latter on dehydrogenation with sulphur furnished the required 4:8-dimethyleudalene (VI) (Table I).

4:5-Dimethyleudalene (XI)

This hydrocarbon was synthesised by two methods, both passing through the ketone (VIII).

*iso*Propylallylacetic acid was condensed with *p*-xylene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to afford a satisfactory yield of α -*iso*propyl- γ -(2:5-dimethylphenyl)-valeric acid (VII). This was cyclised, in an excellent yield, with PPA to afford the ketone (VIII), which like its analogue (IV) was indifferent to the various carbonyl reagents.

Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of this ketone afforded a mixture of the tetralol (IX) and its dehydration product (X). The great susceptibility of this alcohol to water-elimination is understandable, if we consider the conformation of the tetralol (IX); since the carbonyl group is hindered, the lithium aluminium hydride reduction will chiefly yield the alcohol with the hydroxyl in the quasi-axial position (Barton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1027; Barton *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 21) which being anti to the axial-hydrogen on C₇ (the bulkier *iso*propyl group being assigned the stabler equatorial conformation) will undergo a facile elimination; further driving force is provided by the tertiary nature of the C₇-hydrogen and the resultant enhanced conjugation in the hydrocarbon (X).

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

The crude reduction product of the tetralone (VIII) was completely dehydrated with a trace of iodine and the pure (X) dehydrogenated with sulphur to afford the 4:5-dimethyleudalene (XI) (Table I).

The second route utilised the keto-acid (I), described above. The action of methylmagnesium iodide on its methyl ester afforded the lactone (XII). This was converted into the corresponding tetralone (VIII) in a single step, which involved the reductive cyclisation with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 69, 323). The identity of this preparation of the ketone (VIII) with the product, obtained by the first method, was established by its conversion (sodium-alcohol reduction $\rightarrow$ dehydrogenation) into the same hydrocarbon (XI).

TABLE I

	M.P. of the dimethyleudalenes.		4-Methyleudalene.
	4:5-	4:8-	
Picrate	119.5°	97°	102-103°
Picramide complex	161°	164°	...
Trinitrobenzene ..	144°	138°	-146°
Trinitrotoluene ..	55°	...	...
Trinitrofluorenone ..	143°	127-28°	107°

EXPERIMENTAL*

4:8-Dimethyleudalene (VI)

α -isoPropyl- β -(2:5-dimethylbenzoyl)-propionic Acid (I).—*p*-Xylene (freshly rectified over sodium; 39 g., 0.368 M) was condensed with isopropylsuccinic anhydride (Schleicher, *Annalen*, 1892, 267, 114; 47.3 g., 0.333 M) in dry nitrobenzene (520 c.c.)

* All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether employed was the fraction with b p 40°-60°.

in the presence of AlCl_3 (anhyd., 100 g., 0.736 M) in a manner patterned after that of Sukh Dev and Guha (*loc. cit.*). The crude product, m.p. 106° , was obtained in 69% yield. An analytical sample was prepared by three crystallisations from a mixture (1:2) of benzene and petroleum ether as thick colorless prismatic crystals, m.p. 110° . (Found: C, 72.22; H, 8.52; neut. equiv., 247.1. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 72.58; H, 8.06 per cent. Neut. equiv., 248).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) was purified by two crystallisations from ethanol as thick yellow crystals, m.p. 176° . The analysis revealed that no esterification of the secondary carboxyl group occurred during the preparation of the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. (Found: N, 13.0. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.08 per cent).

The semicarbazone was prepared by the sodium acetate method and after two crystallisations from dilute ethanol was obtained as white flakes, m.p. 191° . (Found: N, 14.27. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 13.8 per cent).

The amide, prepared by the addition of liquor ammonia to the acid chloride (PCl_5 method), was crystallised thrice from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether in colorless needles, m.p. 198.5° . (Found: N, 5.4. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 5.67 per cent).

α -isoPropyl- β -oxo- β -(2:5-dimethylbenzoyl)-propionic Acid (II) and its Oxidative Cleavage.—The above keto-acid (2.0 g.) in absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) was added to alcoholic sodium ethoxide (from 0.6 g of sodium and 10 c.c. of ethanol) and amyl nitrite (2 c.c.) introduced with cooling. The mixture was set aside in the frigidaire for 48 hours and diluted with ice water till all the sodium salt went in solution. This was neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid (1:1) at 0° , when an oily product separated, which gradually solidified to yield a crude solid (2.1 g.), m.p. $116-20^\circ$. The material, which gave a positive test for nitrogen, was used as such for the next step.

The hydrolysis of the above isonitroso derivative was carried out according to a procedure of Bartrop *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 181). A mixture of the above oximinoketo-acid (2.0 g.), aqueous formaldehyde (10 c.c., 40% solution) and 2 N-HCl (2 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath for 10 minutes. On cooling, a white solid (1.1 g., m.p. $114-20^\circ$), which developed a deep green colour with ferric chloride solution, separated out; its solution in aqueous sodium hydroxide was yellow. It gave a positive test with periodic acid (Shriner and Fuson, "The Systematic Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1940, p.57) and the test for nitrogen was negative.

The above diketo-acid (1.0 g.) was dissolved in aqueous NaOH (5%, 10 c.c.) and H_2O_2 (5%, 10 c.c.) was added. The reaction mixture was heated on the steam-bath for 10 minutes. This was chilled and acidified with HCl (dil.), when a white crystalline solid separated. On recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, it came out as white needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 132° ; neut. equiv. 149. The 2:5-dimethylbenzoic acid has m.p. 132° (Heilbron, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 1953, p. 284) and neut. equiv. 150.

The filtrate, after separation of the crude 2:5-dimethylbenzoic acid, was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether (10 c.c. $\times$ 4). After washing with brine (10 c.c. $\times$ 2) and drying (Na_2SO_4), the solvent was removed under suction at the laboratory temperature, when an oil was left. This soon solidified and after trituration with a little ice water was collected, m.p. 86-87°, yield 20 mg. This was identified as *isopropylmalonic acid* by a mixed m. p. (Conrad and Bischoff, *Annalen*, 1880, 204, 145).

α -isopropyl- γ -(2:5-dimethylphenyl)-butyric Acid (III).—The pure keto-acid (12.4 g., 0.05 M) was reduced with amalgamated zinc (from zinc wool 40 g., mercuric chloride 4 g., C.P. HCl 2 c.c. and water 60 c.c.) and HCl (C.P., 70 c.c. and water, 30 c.c.) with the addition of toluene (25 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.) by refluxing for 36 hours. At the end of every six hours HCl (conc., 20 c.c.) was added. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solvent layer was separated. The aqueous portion was extracted with benzene (30 c.c. $\times$ 3) and the combined extract washed with brine. The solvents were stripped off and the residue distilled to yield a colorless viscous liquid, b.p. 175-80°/2.5 mm., 198-203°/12 mm., yield 82%. The distillate gradually solidified and crystallised from petroleum ether in thick white prisms, m.p. 77°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 9.13; neut. equiv., 232.3. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.9; H, 9.4 per cent. Neut. equiv., 234).

From the residue, left after distillation of the crude reduction material, a small quantity (0.5 g.) of the starting keto-acid was recovered. However, the use of alcohol instead of acetic acid during the Clemmensen reduction produced a byproduct (0.4 g.), m.p. 201° (from benzene-petroleum ether mixture) which was insoluble in 30% cold alkali (aq.); this was not studied further.

The *amide* crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in white needles, m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 6.3. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{23}\text{ON}$ requires N, 6.02 per cent).

The *anilide* was obtained as white crystalline material from dilute ethanol, m.p. 129-30°. (Found: N, 4.56. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{27}\text{ON}$ requires N, 4.5 per cent).

The *S-benzylthiuronium salt* was crystallised twice from dilute ethanol in white needles, m.p. 139°. (Found: N, 7.01. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{31}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 6.99 per cent).

2-isopropyl-5:8-dimethyltetralone-1 (IV).—To PPA (from P_2O_5 50 g., syrupy H_3PO_4 30 c.c., *d* 1.75) at the steam-bath temperature the above butyric acid (9 g.) was added in one lot and was kept at that temperature for one hour with occasional swirling. The product was poured onto ice and extracted with benzene (25 c.c. $\times$ 4); the combined extracts were washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and then with brine. The solvent was removed after drying (sodium sulphate) and the residue fractionated to yield the tetralone as a colorless liquid, b.p. 141-43°/2 mm., n_D^{25} , 1.5420; yield 78%. (Found: C, 82.88; H, 9.36. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 83.33; H, 9.2 per cent). The ketone failed to yield a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone or a semicarbazone.

4-Methyleudalene (V).—The above tetralone (3 g.) on the Clemmensen reduction with amalgamated zinc (from zinc wool 3 g.), as described above, afforded the corresponding tetralin, which was on rectification over sodium gave a colorless liquid, b.p. 130°/2 mm., yield 2.4 g.

The hydrocarbon (0.55 g.) was heated with sulphur (0.17 g.) at 220°-230° for 1½ hours under slight suction. The product was taken up in petroleum ether (2 c.c.) and passed down a column of activated alumina (10 g.) which was washed with petroleum ether (30 c.c.). From the petroleum ether washings the solvent was removed and the residue distilled over sodium to yield a material (0.22 g.) with b.p. 117°/1 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5765.

The *picrate* was obtained in orange-red needles from ethanol, m.p. 102-103° (Ruzicka *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 103°).

The *trinitrobenzene complex* crystallised from ethanol in golden yellow needles, m.p. 146° (Ruzicka *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 145.5°).

The *trinitrofluorenone* addition compound was twice crystallised from 80% acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 107°.

4:8-Dimethyleudalene (VI).—The tetralone (IV: 5 g.) in dry ether (150 c.c.) was added to a solution of methyl lithium (from lithium 1 g., methyl iodide 10 c.c., and ether 100 c.c.) under nitrogen atmosphere during ½ hour with swirling and cooling in an ice-salt bath. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature (25°) and then decomposed by the slow addition of dilute HCl (1:1; 50 c.c., 20 minutes) with stirring and external cooling. The ether layer was removed, washed with brine and the solvent flashed off. The crude carbinol, thus obtained as the residue, was heated with formic acid (85%, 50 c.c.) for 3 hours on the steam-bath. This was diluted with water and the product taken up in ether. After washing with brine and drying (Na₂SO₄) the solvent was removed and the residue fractionated over sodium to yield 5:6-dihydro-4:8-dimethyleudalene as a colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 123-24°/2 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5355, d_4^{20} 0.9493, M_D 70.2 (calc. M_D , 69.84); yield 1.4 g.

This hydrocarbon (1.35 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating with sulphur (0.2 g.) for 1½ hours at 210°-220°. The product was distilled off and the distillate (0.6 g.) was converted into the *trinitrobenzene (TNB) complex* in alcohol. On four crystallisations from ethanol it separated as golden yellow needles, m.p. 138°, yield 0.95 g. (Found: N, 9.71. C₂₂H₂₂O₆N₃ requires N, 9.86 per cent).

The pure 4:8-dimethyleudalene (VI) was regenerated from the addition compound by filtration of its benzene solution through a column of activated alumina (15 g.), which was then washed with petroleum ether (50 c.c.). The eluate was stripped off the solvent and the dimethyleudalene rectified over sodium as colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 130°/1.5 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5970, yield 90%. (Found: C, 90.2; H, 9.34. C₁₈H₂₀ requires C, 90.57; H, 9.43 per cent).

The *picrate* on two crystallisations from ethanol was obtained as red needles, m.p. 97°. (Found: N, 9.52. C₂₂H₂₂O₇N₃ requires N, 9.52 per cent).

The *trinitrofluorenone (TNF) complex* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised four times from 80% acetic acid to yield deep scarlet-red needles, m.p. 127-28°. (Found: N, 7.08. C₂₀H₁₈O₇N₃ requires N, 7.97 per cent).

The *picramide (TNA) addition compound* was prepared in ethanol and after two recrystallisations from the same solvent was obtained as deep yellow needles, m.p. 164°. (Found: N, 12.2. C₂₂H₂₄O₆N₄ requires N, 12.7 per cent).

4:5-Dimethyleudalene (XI)

α -isopropylallylacetic Acid.—Diethyl allylmalonate (Linstead and Rydon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 586) was condensed with isopropyl bromide according to the procedure of Hjelt (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1855). The ethyl *α -isopropylallylmalonate* (80 g.), thus obtained, was saponified by stirring and refluxing it with KOH (106 g.) in water (140 c.c.) till the ester layer had disappeared (24-36 hours). Working up in the usual manner yielded the crude malonic acid (58 g., 94%), m.p. 103°; a sample was recrystallised repeatedly first from benzene-petroleum ether and then from water as white prisms, m.p. 122-23° (Hjelt, *loc. cit.*, reported m.p. 112.5°). (Found: C, 58.06; H, 7.58. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.07; H, 7.53 per cent). The malonic acid on decarboxylation at 180° for one hour under slight suction yielded the crude *α -isopropylallylacetic acid*, which was purified by distillation, b.p. 121-22°/20 mm., yield 80%.

The *S-benzylthiuronium salt* was prepared in the usual manner as white glistening flakes (water), m.p. 118°. (Found: N, 9.16. $C_{16}H_{24}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.09 per cent).

α -isopropyl- γ (2:5-dimethylphenyl)-valeric Acid (VII).—To a mixture of *p*-xylenes (21 g., 0.2 M) and *α -isopropylallylacetic acid* (14.2 g., 0.1 M) anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (14 g., 0.105 M) was added with stirring at room temperature (no external cooling) during 15 minutes; the reaction was exothermic. The reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 10 minutes and decomposed by pouring on ice (100 g.) and HCl (20 c.c.). The product was taken up in benzene (25 c.c. $\times$ 3), washed with dilute HCl and then separated into acidic and neutral portions by extraction with aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The acidic portion on working up gave the required acid (VII), b.p. 158°-162°/2 mm., yield 11.2 g. (45%). (Found: C, 76.74; H, 10.08; neut. equiv., 246. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 77.4; H, 9.68 per cent. Neut. equiv., 248). The neutral portion was not examined further.

The *piperazonium salt* of the acid was prepared by the method of Pollard *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1759). After two crystallisations from acetone it was obtained as a white microcrystalline powder, m.p. 164-65°. (Found: N, 8.39. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.38 per cent).

2-isopropyl-4:5:8-trimethyltetralone-1 (VIII): (i) *By PPA Cyclisation of α -isopropyl- γ (2:5-dimethylphenyl)-valeric Acid (VII)*.—The above acid (10 g.) was cyclised by PPA (from P_2O_5 , 60 g. and phosphoric acid, 36 c.c.) in the manner outlined above for *2-isopropyl-5:8-dimethyltetralone-1 (IV)*. The ketone was obtained as a colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 132°/2 mm., n_D^{25} 1.5390, yield 90%. (Found: C, 82.94; H, 9.50. $C_{18}H_{22}O$ requires C, 83.48; H, 9.57 per cent).

(ii) *From α -isopropyl- β -(2:5-dimethylbenzoyl)-propionic Acid (I)*.—The keto-acid (1:6.24 g.) was refluxed for 12 hours with a mixture of dry methanol (12 c.c.), benzene (15 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (C.P., 1.4 c.c.). This was worked up in the usual manner to yield the *methyl ester* as a colorless liquid, b.p. 153-55°/1 mm., n_D^{25} 1.5080, yield 90%. (Found: C, 73.11; H, 8.68. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 73.28; H, 8.40 per cent).

To the above ester (5.5 g.) in dry ether (40 c.c.) a solution of methylmagnesium iodide (from magnesium 0.9 g., methyl iodide 4.8 g. and ether, 25 c.c.) was added during 30 minutes with stirring and cooling in an ice-bath. The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature during 2 hours with occasional swirling; finally it was refluxed for 3 hours and left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was well-chilled in an ice-salt bath and decomposed by the addition (15 minutes) of dilute HCl (1:1, 30 c.c.). The reddish ether layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with benzene (10 c.c. $\times$ 3). The combined extracts were washed with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). On removal of the solvent, a pale, orange viscous residue (5 g.) was left, which was distilled to afford a viscous liquid, b.p. 153-55°/1 mm., yield 2.5 g. The material was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution, but soluble in hot aqueous sodium hydroxide solution.

A mixture of the above lactone (2.1 g.), hydriodic acid (7 c.c., *d* 1.7) and red phosphorus (1.4 g.) was gently refluxed in an oil-bath at 130°-140° for 24 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with water (50 c.c.) and extracted with benzene-ether mixture (1:1; 20 c.c. $\times$ 3). The extracts were washed with water (10 c.c.), saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (10 c.c. $\times$ 2) and finally with brine (10 c.c. $\times$ 2). The acidic material (0.5 g., b.p. 157°/1 mm., presumably VII), isolated in the usual manner, was not studied further. From the sodium bicarbonate-washed solvent extracts, the neutral tetralone was isolated as a colorless mobile liquid, b.p. 128°-31°/1.5 mm., n_D^{25} 1.5395, yield 1.0 g. (50%).

1:4:5-Trimethyl-7-isopropyl-5:6-dihydronaphthalene (X).—The tetralone [VIII: method i; 7.5 g.], dissolved in ether, was let into (5 minutes) a stirred (Mag-mix) and cooled (0°) suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1 g.) in ether (50 c.c.). The reaction mixture was stirred for another 30 minutes, while the contents were allowed to attain room temperature (25°) during this period. This was decomposed with ice water (50 c.c.), followed by ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid (10%; 100 c.c., 30 minutes) in the usual manner. The solvent layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (20 c.c. $\times$ 3). The combined extracts were washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the residue gave a distillate with a wide boiling point range (113°-143°/2 mm., yield 6.6 g.) due to partial dehydration of the tetraol during rectification. This was completely dehydrated as shown below.

The above material (6.6 g.) and iodine (30 mg.) were heated together on a steam-bath for one hour, when water separated out readily. To this benzene (10 c.c.) was added, which was fractionated off; this operation was repeated twice to remove azeotropically all the water of dehydration. The residue was taken up in petroleum ether (10 c.c.) and dried over activated silica gel. The solvent was flashed off and the dihydronaphthalene fractionated over sodium as a colorless mobile liquid, b.p. 113-20°/2 mm., yield 5.0 g. (72%). An analytical cut had n_D^{25} , 1.5435; d_4^{25} , 0.9393; M_n , 72.4 (calc. M_n , 69.84; EM_n , 2.56; $E\Sigma_n$, 1.2) (Found: C, 88.84; H, 10.2. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}$, requires C, 89.72; H, 10.28 per cent).

4:5-Dimethyleudalene (XI): (i) From the above Dihydronaphthalene (X).—The above hydrocarbon (4.8 g.) was dehydrogenated with sulphur (0.74 g.) by the method.

described above for 4:8-dimethyleudalene (VI), and the crude product was similarly purified *via* its recrystallised (ethanol) TNB complex, as golden yellow needles, m.p. 144°, yield 3.3 g. (Found: N, 9.71. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6N_2$ requires N, 9.86 per cent). The pure 4:5-dimethyleudalene (XI), as obtained by regeneration from the above complex, had b.p. 138-39°/2.5 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5840, d_4^{20} 0.9706, M_D 73.1 (calc. M_D 69.37, EM_D 3.73, $E\Sigma_n$ 1.76); yield 1.55 g. (Found: C, 90.79; H, 9.50. $C_{18}H_{20}$ requires C, 90.57; H, 9.43 per cent).

The *picrate* after two crystallisations from ethanol came out as orange-red needles, m.p. 119.5°. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N_2$ requires N, 9.52 per cent).

The TNB complex was crystallised four times from 80% acetic acid, when it separated as beautiful red needles, m.p. 143°. (Found: N, 7.96. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.98 per cent).

The TNA additive compound was thrice crystallised from ethanol to furnish deep-yellow needles, m.p. 161°. (Found: N, 12.34. $C_{22}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires N, 12.73 per cent).

The trinitrotoluene complex on two crystallisations from ethyl alcohol yielded yellow needles, m.p. 53°. (Found: N, 9.56. $C_{23}H_{26}O_6N_3$ requires N, 9.57 per cent).

(ii) *From the Tetralone (VIII) prepared from (I).*—The identification of the tetralone prepared from (I) with that of the ketone obtained from (VII) was carried out by its conversion into the 4:5-dimethyleudalene (XI).

The neutral ketonic material (0.75 g.) in alcohol (12 c.c.) was reduced with sodium (1.0 g.) in the usual manner. The crude material (0.55 g.) was directly dehydrogenated with sulphur (70 mg.) as described above. The product was taken up in petroleum ether (2 c.c.) and filtered through a column of alumina (Basic/I; 18 g.). This was washed with petroleum ether (30 c.c.). The solvent was flashed off and the residue converted into the TNB complex, which was twice crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 144°; mixed m.p. with the earlier sample obtained by the other route was undepressed.

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